

EAGER-Investigating Reasonable Costs
NSF Proposal; 2023-05-10

Cover Sheet

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Title of proposed project: EAGER: Investigating “reasonable costs” to achieve public access to federally funded research and scientific data

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Collaborative Status: Non-Collaborative

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Project Summary

Overview: This EAGER project will advance our knowledge of the costs involved in publishing US federally funded research outputs in a range of publicly accessible venues. Using a mixed research model, we will produce insights, tools, and intervention strategies to highlight and mitigate current disparities between institutions and researchers in different research tiers and institution types that may otherwise be exacerbated in the national effort to demonstrate compliance by 2025 with the OSTP Memo on Ensuring Free, Immediate and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research (Nelson 2022).

The Nelson Memo incentivizes national adoption of open science practices and aims to ensure all Americans benefit from ready, immediate, and free access to federally funded research. Even when those digital research outputs are free for users, their publication and management are not “free.” This raises significant questions regarding who should pay for these processes and how much. In a publishing market notorious for extractive practices and perpetuation of inequities in knowledge production and dissemination, public access to research could come at a steep and uneven price to researchers and research institutions. This cost also is likely to be passed on to US taxpayers via inclusion of publishing fees in research project budgets via the “allowable expenses” category unless clear guidance is available.

In this critical moment, as researchers, research offices, scholarly societies, publishers, libraries, and various data management and scholarly communication infrastructure providers actively grapple with emerging policy changes, our research will address core questions: 1) What are the costs of publishing publicly accessible research, and how do these differ across publication types, institution types, and disciplines; 2) What do US researchers and research institutions pay directly or indirectly (e.g., through transformative agreements) to make federally funded outputs publicly available; 3) What workflows and decision chains do researchers and their research institutions use to secure appropriate “public access” channels for research outputs; and 4) How do researchers and research institutions currently establish a threshold for “reasonable cost” for publicly accessible venues and budget this as “allowable expense?” As we conduct this research, we will especially look for differences in both thought and action across institutional types and tiers (e.g., Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCU), Community College, R1 institution, Ivy League).

Intellectual Merit: This project will contribute to our national understanding and response to system, policy, and adoption barriers to open science for federally funded research. It will result in guidance and tools to assist institutions and researchers in understanding their options and what pricing is reasonable for each of those options. We will also demonstrate how different options impact equity and diversity, and what ramifications these effects have on access to the production and circulation of scholarship and research more broadly.

Broader Impacts: This work will provide targeted, evidence-based tools and support to researchers and research institutions nationwide as they determine where and how best to invest in order to provide their federally funded research outputs for immediate public access without undercutting open science values; it will help these stakeholders maintain focus on

ethical concerns, DEAI, and combatting other forms of disadvantage that may result from some “public access” implementation options. It will recommend clear, concrete steps that researchers and research institutions can take to ensure their publication decisions contribute to a healthier, more equitable open science ecosystem. It will also help to keep the American public from unwittingly footing the bill for exorbitant fees charged under some “public access” publishing models, including gold Open Access.

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EAGER: Investigating “reasonable costs” to achieve public access to federally funded research and scientific data

Project Description

1. Introduction and Objectives

The last decade has witnessed a significant increase in publicly accessible dissemination of research findings in the US (Piwowar 2018; Robinson-Garcoa 2020; Simard et al 2022). This has been aided in no small part by a significant uptick in policies by both federal and private funding sources requiring that project outputs, including scholarly publications and scientific data, be made available freely, openly, and immediately to the public (NIH 2008, Wellcome Trust 2012, Holdren 2013, European Commission 2020, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation 2021, Nelson 2022; Larivière & Sugimoto 2018). Responding to the 2025 implementation target for the Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) Memo on Ensuring Free, Immediate and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research (Nelson 2022), research institutions nationwide are working to ready their infrastructures to provide all federally funded research outputs for immediate public access and also to demonstrate their compliance with the still evolving policies.

With the growth in policies, concerns have arisen about how “public access” is accomplished and at what cost to different players in the publishing system (Simard et al 2022; Widener 2022). Major stakeholders have expressed serious concerns about journal publishing models that could undermine the impact these policies have on equity (Olejniczak and Wilson 2020; IPLC 2023; Anderson 2023). In particular, gold Open Access (OA) shifts the charges from the reader to the author, often while carrying forward supra-inflation increases in pricing of journal articles (Grossman & Brembs 2021). Unchecked, such models can continue to drive up the cost of publishing, resulting in increased costs to American taxpayers as federal funding is used to pay the often exorbitant Article Processing Charges (APCs) in the gold OA model (Aspesi 2022).

This is a critical moment in which researchers, scholarly societies, publishers, libraries, and various data management and scholarly communication infrastructure providers are actively planning towards their own implementations of the public accessibility mandates in the Nelson Memo. It is also a key moment to identify the range of implementations emerging and investigate any disparities or challenges arising for specific stakeholder groups, including costs associated with specific solutions. What enablers and barriers impact implementation, including what specific formats and platforms are ultimately selected by researchers and their institutions?

This project seeks to determine how much “public access” publishing costs today for prevalent science publication formats (including articles and data), how much research institutions are spending in anticipation of compliance with public access mandates, and how similar or different the approaches and choices are for research institutions of different tiers and demographics. We will identify the range of implementation scenarios arising in research institutions today while investigating and reporting on any disparities or challenges we find.

To conduct this research, we will engage with existing open data sources (e.g., Crossref, OpenAlex, Unpaywall, DataCite) and directly with key stakeholders, including research institutions (of various tiers and demographics), scholarly societies, publishers, libraries, and data repositories. This research will help to identify and define “reasonable costs” for disseminating federally funded research publications and their underlying data immediately in publicly accessible venues. We believe this investigation is a necessary next step in building equitable access to taxpayer funded research and data and ensuring that the cost of public access is assessed comprehensively, examining the tooling and service options in addition to different business models that are utilized.

The work outlined herein is well suited for an EAGER award both due to the timing of the study (in the window between a policy announcement and its full implementation approximately three years later) and its structure (highly interdisciplinary, mixed research model). The project contributes to a substantive body of research and visualization on open access and public access publications. It complements and builds on 1) research about publication costs and pricing, and 2) research about inequities in publishing that are connected to those costs and pricing, e.g., differences arising across institutional research tiers or types and researcher/research institution demographics including geography, race, ethnicity, and gender.

We will expand and improve upon this previous research into costs and pricing of publications, updating these studies, adding questions about research data publication, and addressing the way the approaches taken by these earlier studies are now compromised (e.g., due to the recent spate of transformative agreements that now complicate the pricing picture).

Our project research will reveal spectrums of practice, including differences or gaps that emerge for specific institutional types and tiers and/or for specific disciplines. We want to empower research institutions to quickly use this research to inform their own efforts to define local policies and practices regarding publication of federally funded research outputs. We will create publicly accessible dashboards, cost calculators, and guidance documentation to assist research institutions in using the data we gather in this project as they work towards compliance with new US federal regulations and policies as described in the Nelson Memo.

This research will be led and undertaken by the Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) team, which was founded to help institutions and funders better invest in the open technology and systems that research and scholarship rely on to further equitable access and participation in research. IOI’s work is centered around providing targeted, evidence-based research, guidance, and support to research institutions and other funders of open infrastructure to help them become better informed about where to invest. The end result of IOI’s work is to improve the funding and sustainability of the sector, improve the adoption and prevalence of open infrastructure solutions, and provide a counter balance to scholarly communication entities that act against the interest of the scholarly community, including the academy.

2. Research Plan

Our project will investigate: how much does “public access” publishing cost today in major publication formats (including articles and data), how much are research institutions charged for such publications, and how are research institutions of different tiers and demographics making progress in understanding how to comply with forthcoming policies regarding public access for federally funded research outputs.

We propose to investigate, map, and analyze this information through engagement with a spectrum of research institutions in overlapping categories that include public and private R1 and R2 universities, research institutes, Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs), Tribal Colleges, and Community Colleges. Our investigation will seek to identify any significant differences that may arise with regards to institutional size, research capacity, economic standing, discipline, or prestige ranking.

As we answer these questions, IOI will also use and build on existing data and research (e.g., Crossref, OpenAlex, Unpaywall, as well as secondary research based on these and other sources) to establish a matrix of options and a cost calculator for researchers and institutions to deploy as they work to determine what costs are reasonable to pass on to American taxpayers via the use of federal funds to publish research outputs in publicly accessible ways. Included in this analysis will also be insight into where funds are currently being directed to advance public access to taxpayer funded research, and where additional attention and resourcing may be required.

Our approach will advance the following areas of inquiry:

- What are the costs of publishing publicly accessible research, and how do these differ across specific disciplines and publication types (e.g., self-archiving vs. post-publication review; peer review)?
- What workflows and decision chains do researchers and their research institutions use to identify appropriate “public access” channels for federally funded research outputs? (Who is involved? Who is responsible? Where is this information reported or recorded?)
- How do researchers and research institutions currently establish a threshold for “reasonable cost” and what they budget as “allowable expense” for publicly accessible research? (What allowable expenses do researchers and research institutions charge to federal grants and contracts currently?)
- What do researchers and research institutions pay directly or indirectly (e.g., through transformative agreements) to make their federally funded research outputs publicly available?

To pursue these questions, we will turn to a mixed-methods research model that will include both quantitative and qualitative approaches, as described below.

2.1. Quantitative Research

The IOI team will collect quantitative data on the publishing profiles and costs for engaged institutions. The project will analyze a range of existing open data sources focused on catalogs of published outputs (Crossref, OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, DataCite), open access status and modes of access (Unpaywall, COKI) and costs of publishing (OpenAPC: previous costing research, including Cramond et al 2019; and ancillary data sources such as DOAB/DOAJ, SHERPA-RoMEO, COKI, Crossref Funder Registry and others).

The project will seek to provide lower bound, and order of magnitude estimates for the mean and median costs for different forms of open access publishing internationally, nationally, and for the consortia and institutions involved in this project, and to identify trends over time (since 2000 to include the effect of previous policy interventions). These estimates will enable the development of a “publishing profile” defining the modes of publishing different institutions use and an estimate of direct costs (including APCs, publishing agreements - where information can be made available). It will also identify the utilization of access modes where costs are deferred to other parts of the research communication ecosystem, including “free” systems and open access repositories, with potential implications for questions of infrastructure sustainability and funding. This is particularly relevant for data publishing and sharing, where direct per-object charging models are rare and costs are consequently very difficult to determine.

Where it is difficult or impossible to obtain direct cost estimates as an input to the modeling (e.g., for institutional self-archiving, where the cost of mixed publishing agreements is not known, or where there are complex subsidies for zero-APC publishing models) we will use a best efforts estimate based on previous literature as a model input, and flag the relevant cost estimates as less reliable. A particular challenge is understanding the differences in costs for repository-mediated open-access across different kinds of organizations with different internal technical capacities and complex internal subsidies.

We will explicitly map the information that we identify as not currently available in order to inform future efforts to improve the ways in which data about publishing costs is captured, as well as to ensure that the design of tools and calculators allows for future inclusion of additional information as it becomes available. The outputs of this portion of the work will include: a) dashboard visualizations per institution and consortial grouping involved in the project, showing the publishing profiles and estimated costs and utilization relative to benchmarks (international, national, consortial levels); b) a model, implemented in a transparent, shareable, and re-usable framework (TBC through the project interviews) that allows the exploration of input variables, with an emphasis on those variables that are difficult to determine from outside data sources; c) a report noting gaps and challenges in the analysis along with opportunities to provide improved data sources, better coordination, or improved modeling of the cost profiles.

2.2. Qualitative Research

The IOI team will also engage a range of qualitative and ethnographic research methods to: 1) study, document, and compare institutional workflows for determining local policies and

processes for publishing federally funded research outputs, including how they will demonstrate compliance with emerging policy guidelines regarding public access; 2) provide context and detailed descriptions regarding how data publishing is managed, what costs are accrued by data managers/repositories, and how much these data managers/repositories charge for public access publishing; and 3) probe discrepancies that emerge in processes and decisions made by institutions of different tiers or demographics.

We will develop protocols for surveys, interviews, and focus groups with each stakeholder type by March 2024, launching our ethnographic research in April 2024. We'll conduct this research based on stakeholder type, with different surveys produced for research institutions (to gather initial information about workflows for decision making at the campus level for policy implementation and compliance), societies (to understand how researchers/members/editors are pursuing compliance and/or thinking about publication within their discipline-based environments), and data repositories (to gather intensive information about each repository's business model, sustainability, values alignment work (e.g., with Plan S and other international leaders)), and community engagement.

We will also conduct interviews and focus groups with each stakeholder group in April-Sept 2024, but will focus our attention on slightly different questions in these formats. For the research institutions, we will focus primarily on the campus process - who is involved, what roles are they playing, how are they evaluating the Nelson Memo and other documentation regarding changes in policy, does that influence where their research faculty are publishing research outputs (articles, data), and how are they monitoring or planning to monitor compliance. For professional societies, we will focus on the researcher experience, seeking to establish what methods federally funded researchers in a specific discipline/field are taking to determine how policy changes will apply to them and what "norms" are expected and/or emerging within their peer groups. For the data repositories, we will conduct deep interviews to understand how costs and pricing relate, and how both are influenced by the market and by expectations from institutions and researchers (including new expectations coming from these policy changes).

We will compile outputs based on each of these threads of research (e.g., a workflows white paper; a synthesis of survey/interview/focus group findings based on stakeholder types). We will also use all of these to help us contextualize and understand how the policy changes are being experienced by researchers, research institutions, consortia, societies, and repositories/publishers in the scholarly communication arena.

3. Engagement Plan

The project will work with four distinct stakeholder types, as follows:

1. **Consortial directors and staff** will engage with us to identify research institutions; they will continue engaging with us throughout the project to learn from and guide our research and findings. The white papers, tools, and guidance we will produce in this project will help consortia to better understand and meet the needs of their constituent research institutions regarding emerging policies about making federally funded research outputs publicly accessible. We have secured the participation of several consortia (Big Ten

Academic Alliance, Historically Black Colleges and Universities Library Alliance, Ivy Plus Libraries Confederation) representing a diverse array of research institutions (letters of commitment are included). Time constraints made it challenging to secure formal confirmation from the remaining consortia (American Indian Higher Education Consortium and Project Vision/American Association of Community Colleges); IOI is in conversation with them and we hope to work with these additional consortia directly. In the unforeseen event that we are unable to work with these last two consortia officially, we are committed to identifying and working with constituent institutions from both of these demographics.

2. **Research institutions** will be recommended by consortia, with 5-10 institutions representing each consortium (30-40 representatives total). People from each of these institutions will engage with us individually and in focus groups. Individually, we will survey/interview/talk with those who are involved in the decision-making and reporting processes around federally funded projects, including those who bear responsibility for determining how to comply with emerging public access mandates. We expect this grouping to include staff (especially from the office of sponsored projects/research), researchers, librarians, and local repository managers from each institution. A “lead contact” will be established for each research institution, and these individuals will gather across institutions in consortial groups to learn from each others’ work as we map the institutional workflows and begin to study similarities and differences in these according to such factors as research team or demographic characteristics. These lead contacts will also gain exposure to comparative data from other consortia about how their members are pursuing similar goals. This group will also evaluate and respond to all research outputs from this project, including the cost calculator and guidance tools.
3. **Professional academic societies.** Staff and members of American Geophysical Union (AGU) will enhance our understanding of the type of activities undertaken by society members as they prepare for policy implementations regarding public accessibility of federally funded research outputs. We will survey this membership community and host focus groups to establish how AGU members and editors are approaching the 2025 implementation, both within AGU and discipline-based circles and within their home institutions. We will also work closely with AGU staff and members to determine what tools and guidance they need in this discipline-focused space to support their members.
4. **Data repository managers and staff**
Managers from each of the seven data repositories (Dryad, Dataverse, Figshare, Open Science Framework, Mendeley Data, Vivli, and Zenodo/InvenioRDM) participating in the NIH Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) will engage with our team through interviews and in focus groups to help us learn with and from them about what it costs, and what they are charging, to provide publicly accessible data in these environments. This research will include attention to differences in disciplines and in types of data. With these repositories, we will surface data about sustainability and business modeling of data repositories, including governance, community engagement, administrative scaffolding, and other relevant features.

During the project, we will also engage with known researchers who have studied cost and pricing and/or demographics of adoption of publication platforms, including Cameron Neylon and Lucy Montgomery (Curtin University), Ludo Waltman (CWTS Leiden University), Heather

Piowar and Jason Priem (Our Research), Vincent Larivière and Marc-André Simard (CoalitionPublica/University of Montreal), Nicholas Robinson-Garcia (EC3 Research Group), and Bianca Kramer (Sesame Open Science). We will aim to inform and request input and engagement with these researchers throughout the study.

Our engagement with broader Open Science circles will come through regular, open circulation of our findings and outputs via IOI's robust network and through all of our project collaborators. This will include two white papers, an open review opportunity for the tools and guidance we produce, and regular open convenings hosted by the project team. We will also deliver at least three presentations on our findings and our research in major open science conferences, including at least one in a data repository or data publishing-oriented venue.

4. Development Plan

Phase 1 (Oct 2023-Mar 2024): In Phase 1 of our EAGER research, the IOI team will collect and synthesize existing literature on options for public dissemination, including their pricing, what access model(s) they deploy, and how their pricing relates to available data on the costs of publishing in each model. This will be released as a CC-BY White Paper reposted in Zenodo: "Summary Review of Research and Publications Defining Costs and/or Pricing for Publications of Research Findings." As we prepare this white paper, we will also engage with known researchers in this area (COKI, Leiden, OurResearch, CrossRef, Erudit/Coalition Publica, etc) to gather their feedback and seek to align our work with theirs where possible.

Also during phase 1, we will begin quantitative data analysis, surveying existing data sets and sources focused on catalogs of published outputs, open access status and modes of access, and costs of publishing as described in "Quantitative Research" above. We will establish lower bound and order of magnitude estimates for the mean and median costs for different forms of open access publishing internationally, nationally, and for the consortia and institutions involved in this project, and we will work to identify trends over time. Using these, we will pursue initial dashboarding and visualizations of this data and establish functional requirements for the cost calculator tool.

Phase 1 will include virtual convenings with all project collaborators, including the following: 1) consortia to identify with each up to 10 member universities and/or research centers that IOI will engage in the ethnographic study components of the project and to build initial engagement of consortial directors/staff to help us understand how to structure and produce guidance (tools, services) that can help their members to plan for 2025 implementations and beyond; 2) societies: to identify with them a set of editors and publications to engage with as key stakeholders in the publishing process for articles and for data and to identify what societies and their members need in terms of tools and services to bolster their planning for 2025 and beyond; 3) data repositories: to define parameters of research into costs and pricing for making data publicly accessible. This group is already working together via NIH research; we will build a model with them rather than imposing one on them; and 4) research institutions: using consortia recommendations, we will conduct outreach and engagement to onboard universities and research institutions recommended by consortia for the ethnographic work slated for months 7-20.

We will also develop protocols for our forthcoming qualitative research (Phase 2) and schedule interviews and focus groups. We will regularly present our findings and encourage questions and engagement from the broader open science community via open quarterly virtual convenings; during this phase, this will especially focus on our initial white paper and our early cost and pricing dashboards and visualizations, plus the functional requirements for the cost calculator tool we will begin to build in phase 2.

Phase 2 (April-Sept 2024): We will continue to refine our data analysis, sharing initial findings (including gaps and barriers to knowledge about costs and pricing) with collaborating societies, consortia, repositories, and research institutions. We will develop a beta cost calculator based on these emerging data findings during phase 2, sharing that for review with all participating institutions during the surveys, interviews, and focus groups that will be conducted during this phase.

This phase will include the vast majority of our survey, interview, and focus group work, especially during April and May, and again in August and September 2024. These will be directed at:

- Research Institutions (Outputs: Workflows for each institution showing decision chains and processes; Synthesis of survey, interview, and focus group results.) We will work in depth with 30-40 institutions, as recommended by consortia, to establish where things flow and where they get blocked for different players/tiers/demographics. What groups are involved in the decisions and compliance reporting around public access within the university? How strict are they about monitoring? How much planning is underway for 2025? How connected are researchers to this process? Who bears responsibility for reporting and/or decision-making/approval processes for budgets? Gaps, tensions, motivations, and process steps will be recorded for each institution using workflow mapping tools.
- Societies (Output: Synthesis of survey, interview, and focus group results) - AGA (and potentially other interested societies) members and staff will provide discipline-based, multi-institutional views of planning and practices around publicly accessible research outputs.
- Data Repositories (Outputs: Synthesis of survey, interview, and focus group results; Cost data; Pricing data) IOI will host initial surveys, interviews, and focus groups with data repositories to surface what influences cost and pricing and to identify the way these costs and pricing relate to sustainability and business modeling, governance, community engagement, and other features of each repository.

We will also begin hosting regular convenings of consortia-based groups of universities throughout this phase, forming cohorts and using these to encourage cross-sharing. Part of the value we see for institutions that participate in this study is the set of relationships they will form or strengthen and the wider window these institutions will gain together into the ways different institutions are establishing (or not!) their own norms, expectations, and processes for compliance with federal regulations/policies on public accessibility.

We will continue to regularly present our findings and encourage questions and engagement from the broader open science community via open quarterly virtual convenings. During this

phase, this will include initial roll-outs of the workflows documentation and the cost calculator tool.

Phase 3 (Oct 2024–May 2025): During Phase 3, we will undertake a comparative analysis of workflows, including variability between institution type/stakeholder type. The IOI team will synthesize this and produce a white paper and visualizations, sharing these first with project collaborators for initial review and feedback.

We will work primarily on developing and finalizing the visualizations and dashboards, the cost calculator tool, and the final workflows examples during this phase. We will also produce guidance documentation for research institutions to help them follow the processes and procedures emerging from our work as “good practices,” testing these with the research institutions involved in our project.

We will continue hosting convenings of the research institutions (to continue helping with workflow review and refinements, and to update these workflows as institutions mature their local processes; to continue sharing information with each other about what is changing and developing locally for them; and to review and help us refine the visualizations, dashboards, cost calculator, and guidance documentation). We will also continue bringing together the consortial directors and staff and the society directors and staff to review all of our outputs, including the visualizations and dashboards, the cost calculator tool, and guidance documentation.

We will continue to regularly present our findings and encourage questions and engagement from the broader open science community via open quarterly virtual convenings and a presentation in at least one open science event. During this phase, this will include refined workflows (including a white paper about these), refined visualizations and dashboards, guidance documentation, and the cost calculator tool.

Phase 4 (June–Sept 2025): During June–July, we will host a convening with participants from across the full project spectrum to review and refine findings, including the cost and pricing calculations, visualizations, and dashboards for outputs of federally funded research (publications, including data publications) in publicly accessible venues. We will also convene the researchers with whom we worked at the beginning of the project (COKI, Leiden, OurResearch, CrossRef, Erudit/Coalition Publica, etc) to share our findings and to plan next steps for research in this area.

Our final phase of work will include the formal, open release of all finalized outputs and the completion of our project reporting. Final outputs will include the tools (visualizations, dashboards, cost calculator), white papers synthesizing our research findings, and guidance documentation for research institutions.

5. Broader Impacts

The project contributes to a substantive body of research and visualization on open access and public access publications. It complements and builds on 1) research about publication

costs and pricing, and 2) research about inequities in publishing that are connected to those costs and pricing, e.g., differences arising across institutional research tiers or types and researcher/research institution demographics including geography, race, ethnicity, and gender. Above all, it will advance open science through supporting policy changes that are intended to improve access to and use of federally funded research.

6. Fit for EAGER

The work outlined herein is an ideal fit for an EAGER award both due to the timing of the study and its structure. Unlike most projects, we are needing to respond quickly to a recent surprise (the Nelson Memo) with national significance to open science practices and to research institutions. The ways institutions are grappling with policy change in 2023-2024, just after the memo's release, is crucial to study and understand. We want to provide these institutions with contextual information (including costing and pricing information) and bring field-level information to bear on local decisions and implementations. The speed with which we can move with an EAGER award is an important reason we are pursuing this pathway. This is also highly interdisciplinary work that relies on a mixed research model coupling data analysis of existing data sources with ethnographic interviews and workflow mappings of current research decision-making practices at a range of research institutions.

7. Results from Prior NSF Support

Both Thaney and Skinner are new NSF investigators and have not served as Principal Investigators on any prior NSF grants.

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